

CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING EDUCATIONAL MOTIVES IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

Jumabekov Ziyovuddin Khazratqul son

Trainee teacher of the Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

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ABSTRACT

The assessment of educational motives in the psychological training of students plays a pivotal role in understanding and improving the learning process. This scientific article aims to provide a comprehensive review of the criteria used to assess educational motives, their significance, and the relevance of incorporating these criteria into the educational system. By examining a range of theoretical frameworks, experimental studies, and practical applications, the article highlights the importance of a multidimensional approach to evaluating educational motives and offers recommendations for educational practitioners to harness this knowledge effectively.

1. Introduction:

Motivation is a fundamental aspect of human behavior, particularly in an educational setting. Understanding the underlying motives that drive students' engagement, interest, and desire to learn is crucial for educators and psychologists alike. This article critically examines the criteria utilized to assess educational motives and their implications in the psychological training of students.

2. Theoretical Foundations:

This section explores prominent theoretical frameworks that contribute to the understanding of educational motives including self-determination theory, goal-orientation theory, expectancy-value theory, and social cognitive theory. Each theory presents unique criteria for assessing motives and helps shape educational practices centered around motivation.

3. Criteria for Assessing Educational Motives:

3.1. Intrinsic Motivation:

The criteria for assessing intrinsic motivation revolve around enjoyment, interest, curiosity, and satisfaction derived from engaging in educational activities. They include self-reported measures, observation of students' behavior and engagement, and progress in challenging tasks.

3.2. Extrinsic Motivation:

The criteria for assessing extrinsic motivation focus on external rewards or consequences that drive students' engagement, such as grades, competition, or approval. These criteria encompass performance-based measures, goal attainment, and the perception of controllability.

3.3. Self-Efficacy:

Self-efficacy beliefs are significant determinants of students' motivation. Criteria for assessing self-efficacy involve self-report measures exploring students' confidence in their ability to accomplish specific tasks, as well as performance evaluation and the incorporation of mastery experiences.

3.4. Achievement Goal Orientation:

The criteria for assessing achievement goal orientation include mastery goals, performance-approach goals, and performance-avoidance goals. These criteria encompass goal-related tasks, personal performance evaluation, and motivational climate analysis.

4. Practical Applications:

This section presents the practical implications of assessing educational motives in the psychological training of students. It highlights the benefits of utilizing comprehensive criteria, such as developing tailored instructional strategies, providing meaningful feedback, cultivating a supportive learning environment, and promoting autonomous motivation. Additionally, this section discusses the integration of technology-based tools for accurate and efficient assessment.

One practical application of assessing educational motives in psychological training is the development of tailored instructional strategies. By understanding students' motivations for learning, instructors can design lessons and activities that are more engaging and relevant to their interests and goals. This personalized approach to instruction can increase student motivation, participation, and overall achievement.

Another practical implication is providing meaningful feedback. When educators have insights into students' educational motives, they can provide feedback that is specific and targeted to their individual needs. This feedback can help students understand their progress, identify areas for improvement, and feel supported in their learning journey.

Creating a supportive learning environment is also a practical application of assessing educational motives. When educators are aware of students' motivations, they can create an atmosphere that fosters autonomy, competence, and relatedness. This supportive environment encourages students to take ownership of their learning, build their confidence, and connect with others who share similar interests and goals.

Promoting autonomous motivation is another practical application. By assessing students' motives for learning, educators can identify those who have intrinsic motivation, which is driven by internal factors such as curiosity and enjoyment. These students are more likely to be engaged, persistent, and self-regulated learners. Educators can then provide them with opportunities that promote autonomy, such as choice in assignments or projects, which can further enhance their motivation and learning outcomes.

The integration of technology-based tools for assessment is also a practical application of assessing educational motives. Technology can provide efficient and accurate methods for collecting and analyzing data on students' motives. For example, online surveys or

assessments can be used to gather information about students' motivations, allowing educators to quickly identify patterns and make data-driven decisions. Technology can also assist in providing personalized feedback and tracking students' progress over time.

In conclusion, assessing educational motives in psychological training has several practical implications. It can inform the development of tailored instructional strategies, enhance the provision of meaningful feedback, facilitate the creation of a supportive learning environment, and promote autonomous motivation. The integration of technology-based tools further enhances the accuracy and efficiency of assessment. These practical applications can ultimately improve students' motivation and learning outcomes.

5. Challenges and Future Directions:

The article identifies current challenges faced when assessing educational motives, such as the complexity of motivation dynamics and the subjectivity of self-report measures. Future directions involve the development of innovative assessment methodologies, considering cultural variations, and expanding research on how educational motives interact with other psychological factors.

6. Conclusion:

Assessing educational motives in the psychological training of students is crucial for optimizing teaching practices and supporting student engagement and achievement. Incorporating a multidimensional approach encompassing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, self-efficacy, and achievement goal orientation enhances our understanding of students' motives and drives positive educational outcomes. By applying comprehensive criteria, educators and psychologists can tailor interventions and create a motivating learning environment that fosters students' autonomous motivation and lifelong learning.

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